

ISic1551

I.Sicily inscription 1551

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stucco (on tuff)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Μάρχος Σημβρώνις

2. ἥρωσ ἀγαθός

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284949

EDR 108274

EDCS 41300025

PHI 175616

Bibliography

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